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THE GOSPEL OF MATTHEW, THE FIRST WRITING IN THE NEW TESTAMENT CANON

Rev. Lecturer ION SORIN BORA, PhD¹

Abstract

In this article we examine the place of the Gospel of Matthew in the concerns of contemporary theologians. The synoptic problem has most affected the traditional approach to the Gospel of Matthew, which has been downgraded from the top of scholars' preferences on the grounds that it is written later than Mark. Another view is that it belongs to an anonymous assembler of existing sources, of which the famous *Q* must have been the most important. The tradition of the Orthodox Church has used the criteria of antiquity and apostolicity to keep the books in the canon. The first writing in the New Testament canon, the Gospel of Matthew, was considered until the 19th century to be the first to be written in the canon. Attempts to resolve the Synoptic problem led to conclusions that contradicted Church Tradition. Thus, Matthew has been regarded as an expansion of Mark or a redaction based on existing sources. The voice of Orthodox theologians was not heard; most considered these theories as unquestionable truths and neglected their consequences for the spiritual progress of the Orthodox faithful. That is why I have shown I have analysed the general character of the ancient papyri, the canons of the first four Christian centuries, the contents of the codices of the 4th-5th century, the quotations from the most preserved Christian writings. All this shows that the Gospel of Matthew was the most important book of the New Testament, the earliest and first Christian writing to appear.

Keywords

Gospel of Matthew, Synoptic Problem, New Testament Canon, Q (Quelle).

The Gospel of Matthew is a reference text for the Church, the first and most intensely studied of the four writings that bear the name of the Gospel. It contributes substantially to a deeper understanding of the meaning the sacred author had in mind. Lately many schools of theology give the Gospel of Mark a temporal primacy over Matthew and Luke, that is, it was written as a time before the other synoptic gospels. The greater interest in the Gospel of Mark is matched by the effort to fragment the texts of the Gospels in order to identify their origin and redactional influences. Mark is usually considered the source for Matthew. The language of the writing of the Gospel of Matthew was, under these circumstances, the language of the source (Koine Greek). Therefore, the existence of the Aramaic Matthew becomes impossible.

This approach to the New Testament canon does not affect the topicality of the sacred books in the vernacular translations of the Bible, much less the order in which the Gospel pericope is read during the liturgical year. Although in the name of scholarship, any theologian can speak of philological or historical evidence, in speaking of God this discourse is of no use. Even if the synoptic problem seems to be no longer a problem, clarified by the theories and ending

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in unanimously accepted solutions, few Orthodox theologians still give credibility to the patristic evidence about the author and time of the writing of the Gospel of Matthew. This is why I believe that a reconsideration of the Orthodox position is necessary.

Criteria for acceptance of New Testament books into the canon

The scientific dilettantism in which the evidences of faith are mixed, including the Holy Scriptures, the only one unanimously accepted by all Christians as the source of divine revelation, makes the information provided in academic communities divergent. On the one hand the patristic arguments for the canonicity of the books are analysed, on the other hand this evidence is contested when speaking of the Gospel of Matthew and beyond. Whatever criteria a Christian community considered sufficient for a particular book to be preserved in worship and read for a direct knowledge of Christ, under the guiding action of the Holy Spirit the books have survived the ages and are today in the corpus of Holy Scripture².

Even though they noted the similarities between the texts of the Synoptics and harmonized them for better understanding, either in the Diatessaron or in collections of parallel texts, the Church Fathers avoided offering rational solutions for the appearance of the books, such as their redaction by late communities, the use of sources by the authors, etc. Their constant concern was to share with the faithful whom they addressed in sermons and writings the grace of God in the Holy Scriptures.

“For the Holy Fathers the apostolic origin was the criterion for accepting a book as inspired Scripture”³. They did not think of a sacred book as a posthumous redaction that preserves the “sayings of Jesus” and betrays the editorial mastery of anonymous writers. Such an origin would have nothing to do with God’s grace. “But as the existence of divine providence is not refuted by those especially who are certain of its existence, but who do not comprehend its workings or arrangements by the powers of the human mind; so neither will the divine inspiration of holy Scripture, which extends throughout its body, be believed to be non-existent, because the weakness of our understanding is unable to trace out the hidden and secret meaning in each individual word, the treasure of divine wisdom being hid in the vulgar and unpolished vessels of words, as the apostle also points out when he says, We have this treasure in earthen vessels, that the virtue of the divine power may shine out the more brightly, no colouring of human eloquence being intermingled with the truth of the doctrines. For if our books induced men to believe because they were composed either by rhetorical arts or by the wisdom of philosophy, then

² Stelian TOFANĂ, *Introducere în Studiul Noului Testament. Text și canon. Epoca Noului Testament*, vol. 1, Presa Universitară Clujeană, Cluj Napoca, 2000, p. 62.

³ Pr. Vasile MIHOC, Daniel MIHOC, Pr. Ioan MIHOC, *Introducere în Studiul Noului Testament*, Teofania, Sibiu, 2001, p. 40.

undoubtedly our faith would be considered to be based on the art of words, and on human wisdom, and not upon the power of God; whereas it is now known to all that the word of this preaching has been so accepted by numbers throughout almost the whole world, because they understood their belief to rest not on the persuasive words of human wisdom, but on the manifestation of the Spirit and of power. On which account, being led by a heavenly, nay, by a more than heavenly power, to faith and acceptance, that we may worship the sole Creator of all things as our God, let us also do our utmost endeavour, by abandoning the language of the elements of Christ, which are but the first beginnings of wisdom, to go on to perfection, in order that that wisdom which is given to them who are perfect, may be given to us also. For such is the promise of him to whom was entrusted the preaching of this wisdom, in the words: Howbeit we speak wisdom among them that are perfect; yet not the wisdom of this world, nor of the princes of this world, who will be brought to nought; by which he shows that this wisdom of ours has nothing in common, so far as regards the beauty of language, with the wisdom of this world. This wisdom, then, will be inscribed more clearly and perfectly on our hearts, if it be made known to us according to the revelation of the mystery which has been hid from eternity, but now is manifest through the Scriptures of prophecy, and the advent of our Lord and Saviour Jesus Christ, to whom be glory forever. Amen”⁴.

Thus, the criteria established by Origen for the inclusion and preservation of books in the canon are their apostolic origin and the unanimous tradition of the Church.

All the Church Fathers affirmed the priority of Matthew, especially on the basis of the specific details of the Judeo-Christian community found in this writing. The Acts of the Apostles reflects the truth of the first historical stage of the Church, which is exclusively consumed within Judaism,⁵ in which all Christians are Jews, and therefore subject to the Law, the Sanhedrin and the Archbishop.

Jewish Christians on the threshold of unconditional acceptance of strangers into the Church through Baptism need a further guarantee that the Lord Himself has broken down the middle wall of hostility between Jews and non-Jews and that every man may inherit the Kingdom of Heaven: “For he is our peace, who has made the two into one, and by whom the middle wall of division has been broken down” (*Eph.* 2:14). So the Gospel according to Matthew is this guarantee that they are to receive all people into the Church without fear of death or punishment, having a duty to go and teach all nations, baptizing them in the name of the Holy Trinity (*Matt.* 28:19-20).

⁴ ORIGEN, *De Principiis*, 4,7, <http://www.earlychristianwritings.com/text/origen125.html>.

⁵ For Bauer (1892-1860), the primacy of the Gospel of Matthew is given by its Judaism. Raymond BROWN, Joseph FITZMYER, Roland MURPHY, *Introducere și comentariu la Sfânta Scriptură*, vol. 1(2), Galaxia Gutenberg, Târgu Lăpuș, 2004, p. 945.

St. Matthew wrote his Gospel for the Jews, a claim made in the 2nd century by St. Irenaeus of Lyons and Bishop Papias of Hierapolis. Eusebius of Caesarea reproduces the information given by St. Irenaeus of Lyons about the writing of the Gospel of Matthew: “Matthew published his Gospel among the Hebrews in their own language, while Peter and Paul were preaching and founding the church in Rome”⁶.

Papias is given precedence in testifying that Matthew wrote τα λόγια (the words of the Lord) for Jewish Christians. He claims to have testimony from St. John the Theologian himself, and writes about 120 the book “Explanation of the Words of the Lord”, quoted by Eusebius of Caesarea: “So then Matthew wrote the oracles in the Hebrew language, and every one interpreted them as he was able. And the same writer uses testimonies from the first Epistle of John and from that of Peter likewise. And he relates another story of a woman, who was accused of many sins before the Lord, which is contained in the Gospel according to the Hebrews. These things we have thought it necessary to observe in addition to what has been already stated”⁷.

Because Papias uses the same term for the writing of St. Luke, until the 19th century everyone agreed that τα λόγια is synonymous with “Gospel”.

It was accepted that the language of the writing could not have been Hebrew but Aramaic, although Matthew, as an official of the Roman Empire (a customs officer), must have known Greek very well. In fact, Blessed Jerome clearly states that the Gospel of Matthew was written in the Syro-Chaldean dialect, i.e. Aramaic. St. Athanasius’ “Synopsis Scripturae Sacrae” places the book of St. Matthew at the beginning of the list of New Testament books, giving the phrase with whom this book opened then and now: Τὰ δὲ τῆς Καινῆς Διαθήκης, πάλιν ὠρισμένα τε καὶ κεκανονισμένα βιβλία, ταῦτα· Κατὰ Ματθαῖον, οὗ ἡ ἀρχή· «Βίβλος γενέσεως Ἰησοῦ Χριστοῦ, υἱοῦ Ἀβραάμ».⁸ This temporal primacy of Matthew, which also gives this writing its place in the canon, can be seen in all isagogical works of antiquity.

The Gospel of Matthew was also listed first in the Muratori Canon (2nd century), based on the age of the writing⁹ and Origen (185-250): “Concerning the four Gospels which alone are uncontroverted in the Church of God under heaven, I have learned by tradition that the Gospel according to Matthew, who was at one time a publican and afterwards an Apostle of Jesus Christ, was

⁶ EUSEBIUS OF CESAREEA, *Church History*, V, 8, 2.

⁷ EUSEBIUS OF CESAREEA, *Church History*, III, 39, 16.

⁸ J.P. MIGNÉ, *Patrologiae Cursus Completus, Series Graeca*, vol. 28 (Paris, 1887; volume 4 of the collected works of Athanasius), cols. 284-93 and 432 <https://www.bible-researcher.com/sss.html>.

⁹ Stelian TOFANĂ, *Introducere*, p. 93.

written first; and that he composed it in the Hebrew tongue and published it for the converts from Judaism”¹⁰.

The existence of an Aramaic version of the Gospel of Matthew, written for and/or used by Jewish Christians, has been widely affirmed. Eusebius of Caesarea reproduces the work of the famous teacher and “imitator of the Apostles”, Panten, who arrived in India and discovered the Gospel of Matthew in Aramaic among the locals¹¹. Church tradition considers that the Gospel to the Hebrews is undoubtedly the Aramaic version of the Gospel of Matthew¹².

The same Aramaic text is confirmed by St. Epiphanius and Blessed Jerome. In discussions on the Synoptic question, the parity of the Greek and Aramaic versions of the Gospel has been disputed¹³. Under these circumstances, an answer must be found to the question: how many gospels addressed to Judeo-Christians are there? If the Gospel to the Hebrews existed together with that to Matthew, the heretical Ebionites and Nazoreans, which in a slightly modified textual form¹⁴, must also have had such texts: the Gospel to the Ebionites and the Gospel to the Nazoreans.¹⁵ Early community interest in book names is low, which is why it is now considered that the fluidity of the names given to books after the communities that used the materials does not prove the existence of distinct works either¹⁶.

¹⁰ ORIGEN, *Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew* (Book I), <https://sites.google.com/site/aquinasstudybible/home/matthew-commentary/origen-on-matthew>.

¹¹ „Pantænus was one of these, and is said to have gone to India. It is reported that among persons there who knew of Christ, he found the Gospel according to Matthew, which had anticipated his own arrival. For Bartholomew, one of the apostles, had preached to them, and left with them the writing of Matthew in the Hebrew language, which they had preserved till that time”, EUSEBIUS OF CESAREEA, *Church History*, V, 10, 3.

¹² IRENAEUS, *Adversus haereses* III, 1, 1; PAPIAS, quoted by EUSEBIUS in *Church History*, III, 39, 16; Origen, *Commentarium in evangelium Matthaei*, in EUSEBIUS OF CESAREEA, *Church History*, VI, 25, 4; Jerome, *De viris illustribus*, iii.

¹³ „It is clear that our Gospel is also based on one of these translations made at that time. The Greek Matthew, however, also depends on other sources, one of which was also used by St. Luke (the so-called “common source”, i.e. common to Matthew and Luke), and another of which is most probably the Gospel of Mark”. Pr. Vasilë MIHOC, Daniel MIHOC, Pr. Ioan MIHOC, *Introducere*, pp. 70-71.

¹⁴ Irenaeus or Epiphanius speak of Ebionites and Nazoreans, those who use the Gospel of the Jews. But these people in these sects were not yet aware that they were separated from the rest of the Church. They participated as before in the services of the Church.

¹⁵ A. GREGORY, *The Gospel according to the Hebrews and the Gospel of the Ebionites*, Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2017, p. 16. St. Irenaeus tells us that this community uses only the Gospel according to Matthew („Ebioniei etenim eo euangelio quod est secundum Matthaeum solo utentes, ex illo ipso conuincuntur non recte praesumentes de Domino”, SC. CCXI, 158-159) so the exchange of names between (*Matthew - Hebrews*) is confirmed here too.

¹⁶ Jeremiah COOGAN, „The Ways that Parted in the Library: The Gospels according to Matthew and according to the Hebrews in Late Ancient Heresiology”, *The Journal of Ecclesiastical History* (2022), p. 7.

This is why we need to look at the differences between the texts, to see if the same book (Gospel of Matthew) has more than one name (Gospel to the Hebrews, Gospel to the Ebionites) or if there were books distinct from the canonical gospel that were lost. St. Epiphanius gives us the Baptism of Jesus in the Jordan, as it was in the Gospel to the Hebrews. We learn of the appearance of a light as Jesus came up out of the water (Panarion III, 13-7), which is why Epiphanius sees the writing used by the Ebionites as a modification of the Gospel of Matthew and not as a separate writing. Origen also says the same in his synoptic explanation of the pericope about the rich young man. Apart from the versions in Matthew (19:16-24), Mark (10:17-25) and Luke (18:18-25), he knows the text of the Gospel to the Hebrews, which is an expanded version of the Matthean text: “It is written in a certain gospel, which is called «according to the Hebrews» (if, however please accept it, not as an authority, but as a manifestation of the proposed question)”¹⁷.

The same is the opinion of Blessed Jerome on the textual differences between canonical Matthew and the Gospel to the Hebrews, without stating that it is another Gospel, but the modified Gospel of Matthew¹⁸.

Thus, the Ebionite heretics and the Nazoreans read only the Gospel of Matthew, which had slight modifications to support their teachings. This fluidity of the text is also seen in Mark, which has numerous variants for the end of the writing, and in Luke, doubled by a Marcion variant (about 150), not to mention John and Tatian's Diatessaron. So the difference in names does not prove the existence of different books, in our case the Gospel of Matthew, that of Hebrews, Ebionites, etc., but the different organisation of the same text for the communities mentioned.

The Synoptic Problem

Today almost no theologian doubts the existence of a textual source Q, from which the authors of the Gospels “take their inspiration”, as well as secondary sources, which are responsible for the diversity of the arrangement of the material in writing, but also for some differences of language, style and content in the writing of the sacred text. Under these circumstances, the direction of New Testament research has shifted towards rewriting the hypothetical Q¹⁹, more than towards understanding the message that the Bible has kept intact, at least from the time of the canon's completion to the present day. “The importance of Q for understanding Christian beginnings should not

¹⁷ ORIGEN, *Commentarium in evangelium Matthaei* XV,14, ed. Ernst Benz and Erich Klostermann, Die Griechischen Christlichen Schriftsteller, XXXVIII, pp. 389-390.

¹⁸ It should be noted that some medieval manuscripts contain the marginalia to the Matthean text with the Hebrew variants.

¹⁹ Maurice CASEY, *An Aramaic approach to Q: Sources for the Gospels of Matthew and Luke*, Cambridge University Press, 2002.

be underestimated. Mark is surely right in asserting that a better understanding of Q will require a major rethinking of how Christianity came to be. Together with the Gospel of Thomas, Q tells us that not all Christians chose Jesus' death and resurrection as the focal point of their theological reflection. They also show that not all early Christians thought apocalyptically"²⁰.

So the existence of Q implies a conflict between the primary Christianity of the Jerusalem Church and the ancient Apostles and the Gospel of Paul. The latter is contrary to the primary witness, precisely by affirming that Christ died "according to the Scriptures" (1Cor. 15:3) for the salvation of men.

After Schleiermacher hypothesized the separation of the Lord's words from the rest of the Gospel, Karl Lachmann (1793-1851) in *De ordine narrationum in evangeliiis synopticis* proposes the literary priority of the Gospel of Mark as being closer to the original traditions, and therefore first in chronological order. The working hypothesis was given by the differences in detail that the parallel places offer. Thus, the tendency to enrich the text through later traditions was assumed, despite the experience of the Church of the first centuries, which excludes and even condemns to destruction texts considered corrupt or even useless. Ignoring this practice of the Church, many theologians were convinced by the phrase "brevior lectio praeferenda est verbosiori rule"²¹.

Mark's priority theory, though initially opposed, was taken up by orthodox theologians in their rejection of the hypothetical Q. Christian Hermann Weisse in 1838 launched the theory of the sayings of Jesus, a source (Q), given priority in time over Mark, used by Matthew and Luke in the composition of their writings. And so the infamous Q made its debut in the theological world. We likewise have Weisse to thank for the invention of the Lachmann fallacy, which wrongly asserts that Lachmann proved that Mark was the source for Matthew and Luke, when in fact Lachmann said the opposite²².

The answer to the challenge of Tradition and the canon as an ordered list is that Mark knew a simplified version of Matthew, so that St. Jerome did not find the Aramaic manuscript of the only New Testament book that appeared in a language other than Greek.

An attempt to harmonize the two theories is found in the Greek theologian Ioannis Karavidopoulos, who is convinced that "the evangelist Mark will continue to be considered the first writer of a continuous account of

²⁰ Eta LINNEMANN, „The Lost Gospel Of Q—Fact Or Fantasy?“, in *Trinity Journal* 17 (Spring 1996) 1, p. 7.

²¹ This principle was rewritten by Griesbach. GRIESBACH, *Novum Testamentum Graece*, LX (canon 1: a shorter reading is to be preferred to a more verbose one). Wim HENDRIKS, «Lectio e Qua Caeterarum Ortus facillime explicetur», *Filologia Neotestamentaria*, 22 (2009), pp. 3-39.

²² Eta LINNEMANN, „The Lost Gospel“, p. 7.

Jesus” as “the first written Gospel”²³. So the results arrived at in solving the synoptic problem give the Gospel of Matthew very limited importance. If there is a common tradition that inspired Matthew and Luke, in the latter we find the older version in common places, while Mark is older and “more reliable”.

The arguments for the priority of the Gospel of Matthew

Orthodox theologians overwhelmingly agree with the common source Q solution to the synoptic problem. They speak very casually about the intention of the author, usually an anonymous person writing in the name of the Apostle, about the Q and other sources, leaving out the many patristic statements about inspiration and the spiritual usefulness of biblical readings. Information about the author, time and place of writing is ignored or contradicted with great ease. Likewise, holding this belief for many centuries becomes a scholarly fallacy in which generations of outstanding exegetes and theologians have persisted.

The shortcomings of this theory have led some theologians to dislike it. Among them are B.F. Westcott (1825-1901), Theodor Zahn (1838-1933) and Adolf Schlatter (1852-1938). In Q “critics have singled out an ancient Aramaic original, translated from Greek”²⁴. “Q and the «Q people» are an historical fiction, no more real than the man in the moon. It would be intellectually irresponsible to rethink Christian faith based on such a tale”²⁵.

All translations of the New Testament and all critical editions of the New Testament (in Greek) begin with the Gospel of Matthew. The motivation for keeping this topicality is custom, respect or Tradition. Anyone who loses sight of this approach, which gives credibility to Tradition, challenges the authenticity of the writing (the author of the Gospel), the integrity of the writing and indirectly, its inspiration, and abandons the criteria that have been the basis for admitting books into the New Testament canon such as antiquity, apostolicity and inspiration.

The Muratori Canon (2nd century) has come down to us without the first page, but the Gospel of Luke is numbered, the third book, preceded by a few words that clearly indicate the Gospel of Mark: “...But he was present among them, and so he put [the facts down in his Gospel.] The third book of the Gospel [is that] according to Luke”²⁶.

The Gospel of Matthew is at the top of all the lists of New Testament books, but also in the codices that have come down to us. Among these lists we mention that of St. Ignatius of Antioch (c. 107-117) and the Anti-Marcionite canon²⁷.

²³ Ioannis KARAVIDOPOULOS, *Evanghelia după Marcu*, translated by Sabin Preda, Ed. Bizantină, București, 2005, p. 24.

²⁴ Raymond BROWN, Joseph FITZMYER, Roland MURPHY, *Introducere*, p. 953.

²⁵ Eta LINNEMANN, „The Lost Gospel”, p. 7.

²⁶ *Muratorian Canon*, 1-2, <https://www.earlychristianwritings.com/text/muratorian-latin.html>.

²⁷ TERTULIAN *Adv. Marcionem* 4, 5, PL 2, 2-396.

Clement Alexandrinus (†215) affirms the canonicity of the four Gospels. The same order is found in Eusebius of Caesarea²⁸, St. Cyril of Jerusalem²⁹, St. Athanasius the Great,³⁰ Rufin (410) and Augustine (430)³¹, Synods of Hippo (393) and Carthage (397), VII Ecumenical Council (787), preceded by Trullan (692).

The fragments of papyri that have come down to us from the 2nd-3rd centuries, even if those with Johannine texts are more numerous (22), among the Synoptics they contain 18 texts from Matthew, 4 from Luke and only 2 from Mark.³² So the interest of the early Church is very low in Mark compared to Matthew. In analysing these texts we see that scribes usually choose to omit fragments of the source text rather than enrich it by additions³³. So the principle “brevior lectio praeferenda est verbosiori rule” cannot be valid.

Even if this statistic says nothing about the order of appearance of the books or the time of their writing, the Church’s interest in the Gospel of Matthew is obvious. No one doubted that this text was contiguous and authentic. This belief has been preserved to this day in the Church’s worship, the clearest proof of which is the Lord's Prayer, which is said only in the Matthean version.

Matthew, Mark, Luke and John is the order of the Gospels found in most Greek manuscripts. The same order will be found in Eusebius and Jerome. Although this order is not preserved in all the codices, the Gospel of Matthew opens most of them: Codex Bezae (D), Codex Washingtoniensis (W) – 5th century, earliest Greek minuscule, Gothic, Syriac (Peshitta) and Old Latin translations, Claromontanus, MS 888, Curetonian MS, Cheltenham, Latin translation of Theophilus, Ambrosiaster (380 AD), MS 498 (12th century).

The Epistle of I Corinthians of St. Clemet the Roman (Rome, 95 AD) sheds further light on the importance of the Gospel of Matthew in the Church of Rome. He quotes mainly from Matthew, following the formula “Scripture says”,³⁴ “He Himself saith”³⁵ or “the words of Jesus our Lord: for He said”³⁶.

²⁸ EUSEBIUS OF CAESAREEA, *Church History* III, 25, 3.

²⁹ CYRILLI HIEROSOLIM, *Catechesis IV. De Decem Dogmatibus*, 36, MIGNE, *Patrologia Graeca*, 33, 500.

³⁰ SANCTI ATHANASII, *Liber de Trinitate et Spiritu Sancto*, 39, MIGNE, *Patrologia Graeca* 26, 1176.

³¹ AUGUSTINE OF HIPPO, *De doctrina christiana* II, 8, MIGNE, *Patrologia Latina*, 34, 41.

³² Peter HEAD, „Observations on Early Papyri of the Synoptic Gospels, especially on the «Scribal Habits»”, in *Biblica*, 1990, Vol. 71 (1990) 2, p. 240.

³³ Peter HEAD, „Observations...”, p. 247.

³⁴ „Have mercy, that ye may receive mercy: forgive, that it may be forgiven to you. As ye do, so shall it be done to you. As ye give, so shall it be given unto you. As ye judge, so shall ye be judged. As ye show kindness, so shall kindness be showed unto you. With what measure ye mete, it shall be measured withal to you” (I Clem 13:2). Unknown text; recalls Mt. 5:7; 6:12, 14; Mk. 11:25; Mt. 7:1-2.12; Lk. 6:37-38.31; Mk. 4:24.

³⁵ „All they that beheld me mocked at me; they spake with their lips; they wagged their heads, saying, He hoped on the Lord; let Him eliver him, or let Him save him, for He desireth him” (I Clem. 16:16). Ps. 21:6-8; Mk. 15:29; Mt. 27:43.

³⁶ Woe unto that man; it were good for him if he had not been born, rather than that at he should offend one of Mine elect. It were better for him that a millstone were hanged about

Matthean quotations are also found in the *Didache of the Twelve Apostles*: “as the Lord commanded in the Gospel” (8:2; 15:3; 15:4). The Epistle of Barnabas introduces quotations by “so it is written” (4:14) “many are called, but few are chosen” (*Matt.* 20:16; 22:14). “The canonical gospels exist. Q does not. The heretical, second century Gospel of Thomas is not binding (unless we are Gnostics). Whether on historical or theological grounds, there is no reason to give up the canonical gospels as the original and divinely inspired foundation for our faith”³⁷.

Conclusions

The order of the Gospels in the current canon must be preserved, even if we were to have a different discourse from the arguments that ordered this list. It is important not to ignore the Synoptic question, but we must not ignore the voice of the Holy Fathers either. It is noted that the Gospel of Matthew is the most quoted in worship and the most quoted in patristic literature. It is true that contemporary theologians also quote it, especially in their own places, but many biblical scholars use quotations from Mark as their primary source.

In the Gospel of Matthew are the fundamental texts for Christian spirituality and many unbeatable arguments in the confession of the right faith in the face of heresy.

The New Testament canon opens with the Gospel of Matthew. The reason for the primacy of this book is given on the one hand by the importance of the category of books to which it belongs and by its age. In the period of the canon’s consecration, the Gospel of Matthew was considered the oldest written book in the New Testament. If theologians have found linguistic arguments for downgrading this writing as a late redaction after pre-existing sources such as Q and M, it is due to the isolation of the sacred text from the community in which it “lived”, being read, believed, copied and confessed. The title of the book says nothing about the language of the book. The Gospel to the Hebrews, as it has been called in the earliest testimonies, is due to the Jewish and Philio-Jewish communities who loved it more than the others.

him, and be cast into the sea, than that he should pervert one of Mine elect (1Clem. 46:8). Mt. 26:24; 18:6; Mk. 14:21; 9:42; Lk. 22:22; 17:1-2.

³⁷ Eta LINNEMANN, „The Lost Gospel”, p. 14.